

Supreme Master Ching Hai World Society

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Entry tags: New Religious Movement (NRM), Quan Yin Method, Cybersect Buddhism, Surat Shabd Yoga, Sant Mat, Hinduism, Indic Religious Traditions, Christian Traditions, Buddhist Traditions, Religious Group, "Divine Presence" Christian Syncretism

As Ching Hai initiates do not prefer to speak of their community as religious, it may be more precise to describe Suma Ching Hai as a transnational cybersect primarily composed of diasporic East and Southeast Asians. Suma Ching Hai is inseparable from a vast mediascape of online lectures, videos, chat groups, commercial enterprises and tightly-controlled official messaging. Sum Ching Hai is also a New Religious Movement that blends together aspects of Hinduism, Buddhism, Christianity and messianic theology. The charisma of the Supreme Leader Ching Hai, called Thanh Hải in Vietnamese, binds the community together. She is often revered by initiates as partly divine, as a perfected being who preaches the proper meditation style (Quan Yin Method) and spreads compassion and the uplift of spiritual consciousness. Born in Vietnam, raised in the West and now based in Taiwan, Ching Hai teaches a syncretistic theology. Based on her time in India, she incorporates Sant Mat traditions, Surat Shabd Yoga (emphasizing divine sound and light), and Radhasoami as practiced in Beas. There are many similar theological touch points: 2 1/2 hours of required daily meditation; spiritual progression through stages of consciousness; abilities to experience astral planes; and total devotion on the spiritual master as an aspect of divinity. Practitioners of Ching Hai are given initiation after watching and summarizing (in written essays) 90 lectures of Ching Hai (available online) and practicing vegetarianism for at least 3 months. They are initiated by either Ching Hai herself or, more likely, by about twenty disciples who are authorized to perform initiations. Children of initiates are given "half initiation" at 6 and "full initiation" at 12 based on their spiritual advancement. Practice of Ching Hai depends on region: in Southeast Asia (Cambodia, Laos, Vietnam especially) and China, governments have branded Ching Hai as an "evil cult" and news stories abound about confiscations of illegal religious material or cult-like forms of psychological manipulation of initiates. In Vietnam, for example, Thanh Hải followers in Hanoi do so surreptitiously, with fear of government reprisal. Their meditation center is secret. Conversely, Thanh Hải followers in Ho Chi Minh City are building an official meditation center and do not live under the same shroud of fearful secrecy. Besides official adherents, there are many people who practice Quan Yin Method privately and consume online material related to Ching Hai without identifying explicitly with a community or even community of faith. The global community of Ching Hai followers could be briefly summarized as bounded together by a range of theological beliefs, meditation practices and forms of digital consumption. Significant communities exist in Taiwan (called Qinghai Wushang Shijie Hui), where the main headquarters were established in 1986. Of Vietnamese origin, several thousand are practitioners and refer to Ching Hai affectionately as Chi Hai ("eldest sister" in Vietnamese). Other concentrated populations of practitioners are in mainland China (although banned officially), South Korea, Singapore, Indonesia, Japan and California. Based on five normative precepts -- which includes not taking life and eating a vegan diet -- non-initiates of a vegan persuasion may discover this NRM by visiting one of 160 or so Loving Hut restaurants -- from Prague to Hanoi to San Jose -- where they will be exposed to Ching Hai's spiritually-infused artwork on the walls and her teachings beaming through 24 hour satellite TV. A cursory glance through online and printed media highlights the importance of veganism and these restaurants in shaping the public perception of Ching Hai (which is sometimes branded a "Vegan Cult" in Vice, for example).

Date Range: 1986 CE - 2018 CE

Region: Transnational Cybersect, East/Southeast Asia, California (predominately among Chinese and Vietnamese diasporic communities)

Region tags: East Asia, Hong Kong Special Administration Region, China, Global, Cybersect, Vietnam, Southeast Asia, Taiwan, Asia

The regions in East/Southeast Asia and the United States most associated with Suma Ching Hai (Chinese: Guanyin Famen; Vietnamese: Thanh Hải Vô Thượng Sư). Certainly there are other Ching Hai followers scattered throughout the world.

Topographic mapping does not reflect the "digital ecologies" that construct match digital forms of communal belonging with new methods of dissemination common to New Religious Movements (NRM).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

—Source 1: Thornton, Patricia M. 2008 "Manufacturing Dissent in Transnational China: Boomerang, Backfire, or Spectacle?" in *Popular Protest in China*, edited by Kevin J. O'Brien. Boston: Harvard University Press (pp. 179 - 204).

—Source 2: Irons, Edward A. 2018. "The List: The Evolution of China's List of Illegal and Evil Cults." *CESNUR* 2(1):33-57.

—Source 3: Suma Ching Hai. *The Key of Immediate Enlightenment* (http://www.shabkar.org/download/pdf/The_Key_of_Immediate_Enlightenment.pdf).

Notes: For a range of print-medium journalism on Suma Ching Hai, see: Agence France Presse (AFP). 9

September 2000. "China Sentences Two Followers of Taiwanese Sect to Three Years Imprisonment." (FBIS-CHI-2000-0909 9 Sept. 2000/WNC) Chua-Eoan, Howard. 1997. "The Buddhist Martha." *Time*. January 20: 47. Claiborne, William. 1996. "Self-Styled Zen Master Has Attained Financial Nirvana." *The Record*. December 20: A40. Goldberg, Carey. 1996. "Cult-like Group Linked to Refused Clinton Donations." *The Commercial Appeal*. December 22: 11A. Nissenbaum, Dion. 1996. "Sect Master a No-show, Rumors Had Ching Hai in Lake Elsinore." *The Press-Enterprise*. December 31: B01. *Washington Post*. 1997. "Unusual Cast of Asian Donors Emerges in DNC Funding Controversy." *The Washington Post*. January 27: A8. _____. 4 May 2000. "PRC Security Targets Taiwan-Based Buddhist Group." *Chinghai.com*. n.d. "Precepts." _____. n.d. "Quanyin." Information Centre for Human Rights and Democracy, Hong Kong. 9 September 2000. "Human Rights Sources Say China Begins Suppression of Buddhist Sect." (BBC Summary 12 Sept. 2000/NEXIS)

– Source 1: *Female Leaders in New Religious Movements*. 2017. Edited by Inga Bårdsen Tøllefsen and Christian Giudice. Sweden: Palgrave.

– Source 2: *The Oxford Handbook of New Religious Movements, Volume 2*. 2008. Edited by James R. Lewis, Inga Bårdsen Tøllefsen. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

– Source 3: *A Historical Introduction to the Study of New Religious Movements*. 2018. W. Michael Ashcraft. London: Routledge.

Notes: For a range of theorization about NRMs and the prominence of female leadership and critiques of patriarchy/ideologies of power, see the above citations.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://suprememastertv.com/en1/>

– Source 1 Description: Primary dissemination of Ching Hai material -- 24/7 broadcasting.

– Source 2 URL: <http://www.refworld.org/pdfid/402a3c7c4.pdf>

– Source 2 Description: Vietnam Country Report from 2003 by the Immigration and Nationality Directorate Home Office (in the UK). Describes human right violations including against Ching Hai followers in Vietnam.

– Source 3 URL: https://www.vice.com/en_us/article/kwkaz9/the-restaurant-chain-owned-by-a-cult

– Source 3 Description: "Vice" article about the opening of a Loving Hut (Ching Hai-associated Vegan restaurant) in California and describes the so-called "vegan cult".

Notes: 1. <http://www.lovinghut.com/images/LovingHutVeganChainStores.pdf> (list of Loving Hut restaurants worldwide). 2. Immigration and Refugee Board of Canada. 2001. China: Meditation practice called "Kuan Yin Famen" (Guanyin Famen, Guanyin Method, Quanyin Famen); treatment of practitioners, particularly in Shandong. 3. World Religions & Spirituality Project (WRSP). Virginia Commonwealth University. Entry by Helen Merianos (<https://wrldrels.org/2016/10/08/suma-ching-hai/>).

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.edenrules.com/>

– Source 1 Description: Primary database for Ching Hai audio/video teachings (in English and Vietnamese) categorized by subject, date, location.

– Source 2 URL: <http://www.godsdirectcontact.org/>

– Source 2 Description: Primary "official" website of Ching Hai advertising her charitable work, commercial enterprises (jewelry, books of poetry/photography, fashion), teachings and world tour locations (among other things such as her daily maxims).

– Source 3 URL: <https://lovinghut.us/>

– Source 3 Description: List of Loving Hut restaurants (associated with Ching Hai and her TV channel) in the USA and globally.

Notes: 1. <https://www.facebook.com/SMCHNewsMagazine/> (The official news magazine). 2. <http://thechinghaicult.blogspot.com/> (Written by a former Ching Hai follower). 3. https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=8&ved=0ahUKEWjS_dqo0lLbAhXHxrwKHVd9D8AQFghRMAc&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.crisis2peace.org%2F

(PDF copy of Ching Hai's "From Crisis to Peace: The Organic Vegan Way is the Answer")

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Ching Hai theology is intrinsically pluralistic and draws on at least Buddhism, Hinduism (surat-shabd yoga) and Catholicism (and other messianic traditions). However, a quick survey of online literature demonstrates that interlocking worldviews -- especially Christianity and Communist-inspired atheism -- are critical of the Ching Hai. For example,

<https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=4&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0ahUKEwiwk5ffYpBhAhWCLpQKHXTBBJKQFghPMAM&url=http%3A%2F%2F>

[supreme-master-ching-hai-religious-showbiz-guru-of-glitz&usg=AOvVaw16JoAzWRUSX0toBIPmPKND](https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=4&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0ahUKEwiwk5ffYpBhAhWCLpQKHXTBBJKQFghPMAM&url=http%3A%2F%2F).

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

— Yes

Notes: Adherents describe how Ching Hai is a community of practitioners of the Quanyin Method and not a religion per se. This non-religious religion tag practically translates into everyday accommodations of other faiths. It is common for a Ching Hai follower (in Vietnam, for example) to perform external Buddhist rituals in a pagoda and practice internal Quanyin meditation simultaneously. However, this kind of pluralism is sometimes rejected by Ching Hai, who encourages followers to follow "wholeheartedly" their first religion (and if it is not satisfying, to leave it totally and embrace Ching Hai with the same wholeheartedness. See: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yMxBeDwDQzA> (minute 23 onward).

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

— Yes

Notes: It depends on the region and local sensibilities. In Southeast Asia, Ching Hai practitioners are sometimes arrested and literature confiscated. In Cambodia, see: <https://www.cambodiadaily.com/news/police-confiscate-illegal-religious-texts-105425/>. In Vietnam, see: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/276220908_New_Religious_Movements_in_Vietnamese_Media_Discourse_since_1986_A_Critic. Despite these conflictual engagements with the media and state, at the theological level Ching Hai often contacts other religious worldviews with value neutrality.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

— Yes

Notes: Occasionally. For example, the Vietnamese government officially banned Ching Hai in 2004 (based on allegations of illegal dissemination of religious material). The Vietnamese media have skewered the NRM as "the most dangerous, evil cults" ever known to Vietnamese authorities and the public." In China, Ching Hai is officially listed as a heterodox "evil cult" (xie jiao) and banned by the central government since 1995. These discursive forms of violence are occasionally met with violent detention and suppression (see: Information Centre for Human Rights and Democracy in Hong Kong. <http://www.refworld.org/docid/3df4be1b34.html>).

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

— Yes

Notes: The debate about the legitimacy of Ching Hai largely plays out through cyber forums from YouTube videos to cult warning websites. Christian missionary groups are particularly interested in debunking Ching Hai even though they may have no direct contact with the organization. These online forums often devolve into misunderstanding and exaggeration and Ching Hai adherents often express hurt and disappointment when they discover such material. Conversely, some adherents have disaffiliated after encountering anti-Ching Hai material.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

— Yes

Notes: The general process for assigning affiliation begins with formal initiation. For a short discussion of the initiation, see: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kReObCngY68>. Ching Hai teaches that formal affiliation begins with the erasure of most negative karma, a boon bestowed by her to initiates. As described in her book "The Key of Immediate Enlightenment" -- "The initiation into the Quan Yin Method is not an esoteric ritual or a ceremony for entering a new religion. During the initiation, specific instruction in meditation on the inner Light and inner Sound is given, and Master Ching Hai provides the 'Spiritual Transmission'. This first taste of Divine Presence is given in silence. Master Ching Hai need not be physically present in order to open this 'door' for you. The Transmission is an essential part of the Method. The technique themselves will bring little benefit without the Grace of the Master." In Ching Hai's Europe International 3-Day Retreat in Hamburg, Germany (1995), she describes how believers must never doubt the authenticity of the Master, but should instead question their level of devotion. Believers should never ask for blessings for anyone but the Master, otherwise they will lower their level of consciousness. The general process of affiliation is bolstered by such warnings about having implicit and total faith in the Master and in her teachings, which are described as the highest level of consciousness.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

— No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

— Yes

Notes: The initiation ritual and transmission are based on the desire of the initiate to raise his or her level of consciousness.

↳ Assigned by class:

— No

Notes: Adherents come from many classes and social segments.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Although certainly Ching Hai especially appeals to women. One adherent described how she really likes that the leader is a woman. If she was a man, people would be more suspicious of him and connect him to politics. "Because she's a woman, she has more freedom. Jesus was killed because he was a man who threatened the social order. [Vietnamese] society doesn't care so much about women - it is more patriarchal - and this gives protection to Ching Hai because she is overlooked and viewed as insignificant." For a more detailed discussion of the critique of patriarchy and appeal to female devotees by NRMs, see *Female Leaders in New Religious Movements* (edited by Inga Bårdsen Tøllefsen and Christian Giudice).

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: As described in her book "The Key of Immediate Enlightenment" -- "The initiation into the Quan Yin Method is not an esoteric ritual or a ceremony for entering a new religion. During the initiation, specific instruction in meditation on the inner Light and inner Sound is given, and Master Ching Hai provides the 'Spiritual Transmission'. This first taste of Divine Presence is given in silence. Master Ching Hai need not be physically present in order to open this 'door' for you. The Transmission is an essential part of the Method. The technique themselves will bring little benefit without the Grace of the Master."

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: After initiation, Ching Hai stresses that adherents do not need to be physically connected with her, do not need to meet with her and can even distance themselves from her online teachings.

Notes: However, they must follow the 5 Precepts: 1. Refrain from taking the life of sentient beings; 2. Refrain from speaking what is not true; 3. Refrain from taking what is not offered; 4. Refrain from sexual misconduct; 5. Refrain from the use of intoxicants.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Not really. Of course Ching Hai herself uses 24 hour satellite TV programming to reach out to potential new recruits. It is more often the case the among the Five Precepts the edict of veganism is most actively promoted as lifestyle worth spreading among non-believers. For example, see: <https://news.godsdirectcontact.net/why-a-vegan-diet-is-the-best-solution-for-halting-biodiversity-loss/>.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: Not only does Ching Hai not have official political support, it is actively suppressed in Vietnam, Cambodia, and mainland China.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Ching Hai often chides her followers to disaffiliate if they ask too many questions about their lack of progress in meditation or about her spiritual authenticity. Moreover, since affiliation is through formal initiation only and then based on personal adherence to the Five Precepts and Quan Yin Meditation technique, there is not a strong sense of communal belonging and therefore apostasy and communal shaming/distancing is rare.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 600000

Notes: Estimates vary. According to <https://wridrels.org/2016/10/08/suma-ching-hai/>, Ching Hai has up to 300,000 followers in Taiwan and 2,000 in California. Certainly there are several thousand more in Southeast Asia. According to the Information Centre for Human Rights and Democracy in Hong Kong, Ching Hai has about 500,000 followers in 20 provinces (municipalities) in mainland China.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 1

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Notes: Ching Hai is not without precedent as a NRM in Southeast and East Asia. It can be best described as a transnational cybersect theologically inspired primarily by Hinduism and Buddhism and placed within a messianic framework which resonates with Christianity.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

Notes: Ching Hai is alone as a Spiritual Master. However, Ching Hai World Society is the corporate entity behind the Quan Yin Method and is affiliated with several other media outlets (World Peace; Oceans of Love Entertainment; Supreme Master Television, among others). The Loving Hut vegan restaurants may also sell her merchandise. These commercial enterprises mixed into the religious messaging require a re-conceptualization of how social hierarchy and leadership is measured in NRMs.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme Master Ching Hai often describes her many rebirths and the acquisition of spiritual consciousness through reincarnation.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: Ching Hai describes how anyone can become a Supreme Master based on the Universal Plan and "karmic pattern of the world at a specific time". (see: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5vKpyfC9Txc>).

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– No

Notes: Suma Ching Hai is infallible and at the time of giving initiation can perform Karmic Annulation (destruction of most negative karma) and Karmic Manipulation (stretching out negative karma to make it tolerable over time). As the Supreme Master, she is considered infallible and partly divine.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Yes

Notes: Ching Hai stresses the scientific and supernatural basis for the truthfulness of her method and teachings. She often chides followers who express doubt.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Scripture is famously elusive to define. Instead of subjective a priori definitions of scripture that hinge on sacred texts revealed by divinity, in the case of Ching Hai it may be more profitable to describe scripture more generally as what it does than what it says or how it was created. Such an approach is ex post facto and draws more closely to phenomenological and anthropological approaches to the study of the sacred. From this vantage, Ching Hai scripture (in various aesthetic, textual and virtual mediums) provides adherents with a moral system (the Five Precepts and countless other social proscriptions enumerated during lectures and transcribed), with a sense of purpose and meaning leading to personal fulfillment, with a sense of bounded community, and with a Geertzian cultural system. With this sense of scripture in mind, the below texts qualify: 1.

http://www.shabkar.org/download/pdf/The_Key_of_Immediate_Enlightenment.pdf 2. Master Tells Stories: Available in English, Au Lac, Korean and Thai. 3. Silent Tears: a book of poems written by Master. 4. Photo Albums: collections of photographs depicting many aspects of Master's life. Volumes 1-13, with notations in English and Chinese. 5. The Wu Tzu Poems: a book of poems written by Master. Available in Au Lacese; and Chinese. Many texts begin with: "Contents and original words in this book are permeated with grace and blessings of Supreme

Master Ching Hai."

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: For the most comprehensive database of audio/video lectures of Ching Hai, see: <http://www.edenrules.com/index.php?route=product/category&path=59>

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

Notes: The scriptures (oral and textual) are so closely bound up with the digital dissemination of religious material as a cyberspace that most adherents understand the commingling of commerce and theology that is both its origin and perpetuation.

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: However, multiple and changing additions are available of "sacred texts" and oral scriptures and theological precepts have changed over time. Ching Hai is particularly unclear about the role of wealth/poverty in attaining spiritual consciousness. She sometimes affirms a prosperity doctrine and other times promotes the creativity, spirituality and even "fun" of poverty. Critics latch onto this scriptural ambiguity as a dissembling technique to raise donations.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: Ching Hai organizes transnational tours during which she propounds on the scripture. Many online videos and published materials are available which show employees of Suma Ching Hai International Association asking for points of theological clarification to Ching Hai. Ching Hai alone offers interpretation.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Notes: While Suma Ching Hai International Association formally disseminates the scripture, what is striking is how decentralized scriptural transmission is through various digital media. There are dozens of private websites, social media websites and YouTube channels dedicated to promoting Ching Hai and offering personal testimonials.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Notes: The totality of videos, lectures, art books, poetry books, texts written by Ching Hai (or composed of her transcribed speeches) and even literature/posters available at Loving Hut restaurants all constitute a very loose and decentralized canon that change based on country and the personal temperament of the believer.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: However, adherents describe how the attainment of levels of consciousness physically mark believers as distinct from the general population. One could argue that the logo of Loving Hut is itself a kind of iconography -- a heart with Chinese characters inside and green English writing along the outer rim: "Go Veg, Go Green". Other markers of Suma Ching Hai are her eccentric outfits (always changing and designed in part to be sensitive to the culture in which she is giving lectures) and her trademark white "vegan" fur jacket. The Supreme Master TV channel is itself a kind of iconography that has a clear infomercial-like aesthetic and jumbled, quick-running polyglot translations (in as many as 14 languages at one time).

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

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Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– No

Notes: However, the Loving Hut restaurants sometimes function as sacred sites and places of meditation. As described above, they are replete with sacred symbols (usually paintings and statues manufactured by Ching Hai and purportedly made by her) which transmit spiritual teachings and power.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The physical body is described as essential for spiritual practice. "The longer you stay in it, the better for you -- the longer you can practice and your level will be higher based on the

health of your physical body." Being able to chose a human birth demonstrates the merit of your karma from past lives. So while the spirit/body dichotomy is strong, Ching Hai does not denounce the body. See: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aKLRkWiJRSs>

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: According to Ching Hai, we are all "mini gods" because we are part of the whole of God. The divinity in us is ontologically distinct from the body although it is helped by healthy material human bodies. However, we have forgotten our share of divinity as we make compromises to exist in this world and get trapped in the material/embodied self. See: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zUP2EgjOwaY>

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: Ching Hai teaches a version of afterlife similar to Tibetan Buddhism. For example, she encourages adherents to follow the harsh Buddha Light as described in the Bardol Thodol and not get stuck in astral existence. See: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YIZEN_SUoqY. Ching Hai offers teachings on how to prepare for the afterlife. See: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0BNzE0VGLT0>.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

Notes: Buddhaland and The Kingdom of God (Buddhist and Christian) are used interchangeably.

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: Described as a privileged form for reaching supreme mastery.

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: See: <http://godsdirectcontact.eu/eng/teachings/t-karma.htm>. It is worth noting that

Ching Hai often quotes the Bible ("As you sow, so shall you reap") as an equivalent idea of karmic consequence within Christianity.

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:
– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:
– No

Notes: Although Ching Hai offers several discussion about cremation during moral teachings, there is no formal theology concerning the treatment of corpses.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:
– No

Are grave goods present:
– No

Notes: Not as theologically required, but Asian practitioners coming from a Buddhist background influenced by Chinese popular practices regarding ancestor worship may offer special kinds of grave goods.

Are formal burials present:
– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:
– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:
– Yes

Notes: Ching Hai often preaches God Quality (GQ) which is variable within us all. She likens humans to light bulbs of different wattage and the electricity the GQ. Supreme Masters are those individuals of the highest GQ.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
– Yes

Notes: Ching Hai theology is complicated in this regard. Ching Hai is considered a "Supreme Living Master" who can give "direct contact with God". She is also considered partly divine. She often describes the highest emanations of God as an essence, a wattage, and she is currently the sole Supreme Master who has reincarnated in human form to spread compassion and teaching like a Buddhist Bodhisattva.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
– No

Notes: Emphasis is on light and sound as manifestation of divinity. Supreme Master does not emphasize geographic locality of the high god.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supreme Master emphasizes the goodness of faith similar to prosperity gospel in the Evangelical tradition. For example, she often praises the merit and fortune of her followers for having discovered her teachings. She emphasizes that God is spoiling them if only they accept the gifts from God.
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Yes [specify]: Emphasis on light and sound and sameness with self-actualized believer.
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No
 - ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
 - ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Supreme Master emphasizes the dual sameness of the believer and high god -- so that knowledge of self is knowledge of God, and vice-versa. For example: Do not forget that you have your own goodness inside you. Do not forget that you have God dwelling within your body. Do not forget that you have Buddha within your heart
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: This is theologically tricky: in some teachings, the self and God fuse through inner knowledge. In other teachings, karmic laws are given priority (creating the expected karmic causality found in Hinduism and Buddhism).
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: This depends on the interpretation of specific followers.

- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Emphasis is on how following Supreme Master is not a religious path and one should not renounce another faith tradition. Instead, the spirituality of Supreme Master is constructed as hybrid and syncretistic, and much theological material directly cites scripture from other religions.
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Light and south are given prominence.
- ↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: This depends on if you view the high god as an aspect of the realized self or as a discrete entity.
- ↳ Previously human spirits are present:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
 - Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.
 - Yes
 - Notes: A variety of ethical claims and prosocial norms around goodness, animal rights and suffering bind the community. The restaurants function as both community meeting places and reminders of the moral normative claims around veganism.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes

- ↳ Incest:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Yes [specify]: Under the Five Guidelines: Refrain from Sexual Misconduct.
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - No
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
 - No
- Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:
- No
- Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:
- Yes
- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - Yes
- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - No
- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:
 - No
- ↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:
 - No
- ↳ Done randomly:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:
 - Field doesn't know
 - Notes: Although many references are made to heaven, Supreme Master most often emphasizes the imperative to create heaven on earth within this temporality. She often describes heaven as the Buddha Land of Amitabha and access is not through death but through initiation and raising consciousness while alive.
- ↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:
 - Field doesn't know
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
 - Yes
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [specify]
 - Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?
 - Yes
 - ↳ Alive, identified:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Ching Hai identifies her current incarnation within the succession of messianic figures including Moses, Buddha, Jesus and Mohammad.
 - ↳ Coming in this lifetime:
 - No
 - ↳ Coming on specified date:
 - No
 - ↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:
 - No
 - ↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:
 - No
 - ↳ Coming has already passed:
 - No
 - ↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:
 - No
 - ↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:
 - Yes
 - Notes: To teach the proper mode of meditation -- the Quan Yin Method -- increase compassion and aid practitioners in raising their God Quality.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Ching Hai does not strictly require celibacy. Her attitude about sexuality can be nicely summarized here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G2ddC1FMXis>

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Notes: Ching Hai generally preaches monogamy to store up energy and focus for meditation. See: <http://sos-klimawandel.info/eng/meditation/refrain-4.htm>

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Suma Ching Hai said in a teaching about juice fasting: "It is not just a one week fast, it also awakens our inner courage. At least in a short period of time after the fast, you would have the courage that you can do anything and you can fast for an even longer time, let alone just change to a vegetarian or vegan diet. Therefore, after one or two weeks of fasting, you would feel you are invincible."

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Notes: Veganism is at the heart of the normative ethics of Ching Hai. She describes the all-loving, all-constructive force of veganism which can melt away negative energy. The first of the Five Precepts is to "refrain from taking the life of sentient beings" (which necessarily entails veganism). For an example of Ching Hai's cooking classes, see: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tJUA2ZPqIhA>; For an example of ethical teachings about veganism, see: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9wW3SjPubLw>.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: However, many media outlets and scholars of cult followings warn about the coercive techniques of extracting wealth from followers.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Attendance at Ching Hai teachings and workshops, for example. Much time is spent consuming digital archives of Ching Hai's broadcasting. But there are not formal, regularized services.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that Ching Hai is banned in several countries, restricted in others. Followers often describe feeling attacked (most directly through online venues such as anti-Ching Hai chat boards and websites). The media (Western and otherwise) is littered with quick exposes attacking the "vegan cult". This creates some sense of risk (and then there is the real risk of arrest or harassment in Southeast Asia and China).

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The Five Precepts.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Not required, but often happening.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Notes: Although membership in the community is focused on small-scale rituals (such as household meditation, visits to Loving Hut, trips to Ching Hai retreats and so on).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: Large-scale rituals could be construed as trips to retreats based on Ching Hai's international tour.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: Although some members wear Ching Hai's jewelry as objects of religious devotion imbued with her power and also markers of identity in a social sense.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– No

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Notes: "Brothers" and "Sisters" fictive kinship terms are frequently used.

- ↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:
 - Yes

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A transnational Buddhist/surat-shabd/messianic cybersect

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

- Yes

Notes: <https://news.godsdirectcontact.net/lia-reports/assisting-red-cross-alleviate-hunger-famine-170594/>

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Notes: Various forms of relief may be supplied by state governments based on the location of Ching Hai practitioners.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

- Yes

Notes: Ching Hai teaches sharing wealth as central to her teaching. See: <http://www.godsdirectcontact.org.tw/eng/news/155/qa3.htm>. For a list of self-reported charitable donations through the "Love in Action" assistance program, see: <https://news.godsdirectcontact.net/lia-reports/expenditures-supreme-master-ching-hai-international-association-charitable-relief-activities-formosa-november-2014-june-2015/>.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Notes: State governments and other NGOs.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

- Yes

Notes: As reported through Love In Action: "Before Tét Quý Ty (New Year of the Snake) in 2013, Supreme Master Ching Hai sent a gift of US\$20,000 and asked our Association members to kindly use the sum to help the elderly individuals living alone or in hardship." It goes on to describe (with pictures) the charitable donations to elderly citizens.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Notes: Various state governments and NGOs.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

- No

Notes: The policy is that children must wait until 18 to become initiates. An exception, however, is made for children of parents who are already initiates. For those children, they are taught "half-initiation" at as young as six years old, and can become full initiates at 12 years old.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

- Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

- Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: This is highly variable based on individual adherent. Some do not interact with the bureaucracy after initiation. Their interaction is limited to contacting the "contact person" for the area in which they live. See website for list here: <http://www.godsdirectcontact.org.tw/eng/cp/index.htm>. Potential initiates are instructed to summarize 90 lectures by Suma Ching Hai, be vegan for at least 3 months, and then wait for a formal initiation ceremony. They are instructed in proper Quan Yin meditation method, after which time they may maintain close ties to the bureaucracy (through local centers and headquarters) or move into a more liminal engagement with official bureaucratic organization (limited more to the consumption of Supreme Master TV and related official websites).

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: State and local bureaucracies.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The charitable wing of Ching Hai provides various forms of relief to refugees, the poor, infirm and elderly. Some critics of Ching Hai claim that there is not an equitable redistribution of donations.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: In San Jose, for example, a collection box is passed around at the Center and people give anonymously. There is not a formal set amount one should donate. In addition to tithing, many adherents are eager to buy Ching Hai-related products (jewelry, paintings, statues, photo books, fashion and so on) to feel connected to her.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: State and local taxes and whatever tithes are required from adherents based on their other religious affiliations.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In some countries in East and Southeast Asia, Ching Hai is branded an "evil cult" by the government and police have notably arrested Ching Hai followers and charged them with illegal dissemination of religious material.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Various government judicial systems based on location.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Most Ching Hai initiates describe Suma as a friend foremost and not a punishing/wrathful teacher. However, Ching Hai can strongly condemn doubtful or self-focused practitioners and that social shaming is a kind of powerful punishment in itself.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Disaffiliation among Ching Hai practitioners is not strongly condemned as many adherents are loosely interconnected as a transnational cyberspace and so strong forms of communal ostracism are not possible.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Notes: Not exile, but Ching Hai practitioners are more likely to find religious freedoms in the diaspora outside Southeast and East Asia.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The Five Precepts and veganism above all.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Many Ching Hai followers practice with fear of reprisal from the military, government and

media. Several adherents described to me being harassed by Christians and atheists for practicing a cult. For one such case of detention and suspicion in Cambodia, see: <https://www.cambodiadaily.com/news/police-confiscate-illegal-religious-texts-105425/>.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

— No

Notes: Not its own distinct written text. However, one feature of Ching Hai is the linguistic gender blurring of God. For example: She + He = Hes (như trong từ Bless); Her + Him = Hirm (như trong từ Firm); Hers + His = Hiers (như trong từ Dear)

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

— Yes

Notes: May 8th is Ching Hai's birthday and an important celebration. Many adherents are aware of Ching Hai's lecture tour, which provides an important chance to gain initiation and hear her teachings. For an example of her 1999 tour, see: <http://www.godsdirectcontact.org/eng/lecture/tour99/>.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

— No

Notes: Although the Loving Hut restaurants (and other vegan restaurants associated with Ching Hai) are important sites of communal feasting and opportunities to preach the theology of veganism to the wider community. For an example of this in San Jose, see: <https://www.vegetarianhouse.us/about.html>.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No